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 Integration of heterogeneous Data and Evidence towards
 Regulatory and HTA Acceptance

WP4 – Healthcare data standards and interoperability

D4.2 – Data Standards Manual

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1. Introduction to the IDERHA Data Standards

1.1 IDERHA's mission and objective

The IDERHA project (Integration of Heterogeneous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory and HTA Acceptance: <https://www.iderha.org>) is establishing a federated data infrastructure architecture that enables remote nodes to connect securely with data holders within a healthcare data environment. This framework ensures that individuals' health data is prepared and accessible to facilitate its secondary use for research and analysis. IDERHA employs Artificial Intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) algorithms, which have been validated on synthetic or pseudonymized data. These algorithms use multimodal and imaging data sources to enhance the efficiency and accuracy of risk profiling, malignancy risk prediction, diagnosis, and prognosis of lung cancer patients. IDERHA is one of the Innovative Health Initiative (IHI)¹ research projects, launched in April 2023 and will run for 5 years until March 2028.

IDERHA aims to provide solutions to overcome the gaps in current data standards and data integration problems within the healthcare domain, with the main goal of creating a federated infrastructure that allows existing platforms to connect and integrate with new health data sources. This infrastructure will enable the collection and accessibility of specific health data for supporting secondary use. Moreover, IDERHA will leverage AI and ML algorithms to enhance prediction and diagnostic capabilities related to lung cancer, applying them to different stages of the lung cancer patient journey. Furthermore, IDERHA will develop a digital application that facilitates remote monitoring of individual health statuses through wearable devices, enhancing patient engagement after discharge. This digital solution aims to accelerate discharge processes and provide personalized healthcare management, hence improving overall patient outcomes.

1.2 Data Standards Manual Objective

The current document provides an overview of the standards, ontologies and guidelines used in the IDERHA project. It is delivered as Deliverable(D) 4.2 due at Month(M)24, within the IDERHA healthcare data standards and interoperability work package (WP4). This data standards manual was developed under the coordination of the University of Luxembourg (UNILU) team, in collaboration with the consortium partners. These state-of-the-art standards and associated technical requirements would facilitate both federated data processing approaches and the implementation of the FAIR principles (Findability, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable)² throughout the project. Furthermore, all internal and external data holders connecting to the IDERHA data network should comply with these data standards. Data holders should align with them while supporting the secondary use of data within IDERHA.

During the development of IDERHA data standard manual, we explored existing recommendations and ongoing initiatives to address some of the gaps in the current data standards. It encompasses several key aspects for effective health data management (clinical data, metadata, Environmental, Socioeconomic, AI model representation standards, etc.) and presents related standards for each aspect. It provides interoperability standards, vocabularies, and guidelines to achieve a high level of health data quality. In IDERHA, the quality of data is further assessed using the IDERHA Data Quality (DQ) framework, which is later described in this document. The

manual also includes recommendations for sharing and exchanging generic and biological data. Furthermore, it proposes standards for the exchange of patient-generated data, defines criteria for quality and performance measurement, and recommends several data-sharing standards specifically for AI models. The set of standards proposed in this document will support the FAIR principle metrics across the IDERHA project.

IDERHA aims to interconnect heterogeneous, multi-source health data resources. Some data types, such as citizen-generated health data from consumer and medical devices like wearables and telemonitoring applications used in home settings, can lack established compatible data standards. This data standards manual will address the data standards associated with the establishment of a federated AI infrastructure and the sharing of AI models for secondary use.

1.3 Intended Audience

The target audience for this document includes:

- Researchers, data users and data holders aiming at increasing their understanding of IDERHA data standards and principles.
- Clinical and technical teams at the healthcare data provider's site are aiming to facilitate the establishment of OMOP-based data repositories.
- Software developers are aiming to develop patient applications and AI models over the IDERHA federated data infrastructure.
- Data scientists and data managers are aiming to assist in the use of data harmonization tools and frameworks.

1.4 Gaps in Current Data Standards

The European Health Data & Evidence Network (EHDEN)³ and the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) initiatives have made progress toward creating a standardized, federated health data network across the European Union (and beyond) using the Observational Medical Outcome Partnership Common Data Model (OMOP-CDM)⁴. Currently, OMOP CDM is a well-known standard that enables researchers to conduct large-scale, multi-site analyses and generate reliable evidence. Hence, we have selected it as our primary data standard for data harmonization. However, OMOP-CDM does not cover all categories of health data, particularly in standardizing areas such as environmental exposure, medical devices, patient-reported experience measures/patient-reported outcome measures (PREMs/PROMs) and all aspects of cancer data (e.g., disease site, rare diseases)⁵. Currently, some work groups within the OHDSI community are working on providing extensions to OMOP CDM for these categories of data, for instance, oncology and medical imaging working groups^{6,7}. There are several standards and extensions presented for each of these data categories separately (e.g., OMOP imaging, OMOP-Genomics, Patient Reported Outcomes (PRO) FHIR, etc.). However, there is a lack of common data model agreement among data holders for running federated data processing in the secondary use of health data. The Lack of common standards and data model agreements leads to custom-made, inefficient, and time-consuming approaches that complicate processing heterogeneous data.

Most of the current common data models, like Health Level 7 Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise (HL7 IHE) profiles⁸, are concerned with the exchange of data in primary care. Additionally, differences in local data and terminologies (e.g. cancer terminologies, socioeconomics, etc.) might introduce inconsistencies. Finally, data transformation to OMOP-CDM can also be resource-intensive, often requiring considerable data mapping and transformation efforts⁹⁻¹¹.

To address these potential gaps, we will agree on and recommend relevant standards to cover IDERHA requirements, which are not currently addressed by OMOP-CDM. This will be addressed throughout this document and its subsequent updates. The IDERHA data standard manual includes standards for metadata, molecular genetics and biology, socioeconomics, and environmental health data and etc.. We also introduce a set of tools supporting health data interoperability and harmonization to facilitate data mapping and curation and to comply with the proposed data standards.

1.5 Data Standards Selection Procedure

The IDERHA consortium decided on OMOP CDM and OHDSI standardized vocabularies as the base standards. For all additional subjects/applications not covered by OMOP-CDM, related well-known standards were identified using different organizations and communities, including OHDSI, ISO, W3C¹², FHIR¹³, CDISC¹⁴, and eTRIKS Starter Pack¹⁵. The requirements from other IDERHA work packages (WPs 1-3, 5, and 6), such as the data format for input in computational models (WP2), were collected, leading to recommendations for different data scopes that would build a foundational framework for the data integration and the development of federated AI algorithms and tools. The identified standards were then further discussed in internal WP4 meetings and communicated with all IDERHA work packages.

As the IDERHA project use cases and requirements evolve within the project duration, additional health data standards or specifications may be added to further versions of the IDERHA Data Standard Manual. The selection of data standards in IDERHA was an iterative process, considering the IDERHA project's use cases and priorities. Following project-level discussions, the IDERHA WP4 on Data Standards elaborated this manual, which was reviewed by all IDERHA WPs. After this, the complete IDERHA Data Standards Manual was shared with related stakeholders.

1.6 Acronyms

A brief glossary of the terms used in this data standards manual is provided in Table 1. A detailed glossary for the terms used in the IDERHA project is being developed by the “Ethical and legal framework” in work package (WP5) and is available to the IDERHA project members in the project’s SharePoint at [\(European Health Data & Evidence Network \(EHDEN\), n.d.\)](#).

Table 1. IDERHA Data Standard Manual Acronyms

AAI	Authentication & Authorization Infrastructure
AI/ML	Artificial Intelligence / Machine Learning
API	Application Programming Interface

BAM	Binary Alignment/Map
BCF	Binary Call Format
CDISC	Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium
CDM	Common Data Model
CRAM	Compressed Reference-based Alignment
DAC	Data Access Committee
DCAT	Data Catalog Vocabulary
DICOM	Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine
DIPA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DMP	Data Management Plan
DQ	Data Quality
DQD	Data Quality Dashboard
DRM	Digital Rights Management
DURI	Data Use & Researcher Identities
EDEN	European Health Data & Evidence Network
EEA	European Environment Agency
EHDS	European Health Data Space
EHR	Electronic Health Records
eIDAS	Electronic Identification, Authentication, and Trust Services
Eionet	European Environment Information and Observation Network
EMA	European Medicine Agency
EMR	Electronic Medical Record
ESeC	European Socio-Economic Classification
ETL	Extract, Transform and Load
FAIR	Principles of Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability and Reusability
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
FML	Federated Machine Learning
fMRI	Functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging
G-CDM	Genomic Common Data Model
GA	Grant Agreement
GA4GH	Global Alliance for Genomics and Health
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
GML	Geography Markup Language

HGNC	Human Genome Organization Gene Nomenclature Committee
HL7	Health Level 7
IDERHA	Integration of heterogenous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory & HTA Acceptance
IG	Information Governance
IHE	Integrating the Healthcare Enterprise
IHI	Innovative Health Initiative
IMI	Innovative Medicine Initiative
INSPIRE	Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community
MI WG	Medical Imaging Working Group
NFPs	National Focal Points
NGS	Next Generation Sequencing
NIFTI	Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative
OHDSI	Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
ORDL	Open Digital Rights Language
PHD	Personal Health Data
PoC	Point of Care
PRO	Patient Reported Outcome
PROM	Patient Reported Outcome Measures
RDF	Resource Description Framework
SAM	Sequence Alignment/Map
SDOH	Social Determinants of Health
SDTM	Study Data Tabulation Model
SDTMIG-MD	Study Data Tabulation Model (SDTM) Implementation Guide for Medical Device
SNOMED	Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine
TEHDAS	The Joint Action Towards the European Health Data Space
UNILU	University of Luxembourg
VA	Variant Allele
VCF	Variant Call Format
VRS	Variant Representation Specification

2. IDERHA Data Standards

In this section, we present the main data standards used in IDERHA. These include the canonical OMOP-CDM, controlled vocabularies and other main identified data categories including: metadata, imaging data, Molecular Genetics and Biology data, socioeconomics and environmental data.

2.1 Observational and Clinical Data

The OMOP-CDM is a publicly available data standard aiming to standardize observational data to facilitate effective data analytics that yield trustworthy health research. This standardization enables uniform analytics that leverage the integrated data for creating feature characterization, outcome estimation and conducting clinical prediction studies¹⁶. This approach involves converting data from various/ multiple sources into a unified data model and a standardized representation for structure and content (Figure 1), allowing systematic processing through a set of standard analytic routines designed for the common format. Controlled vocabularies, which are considered one of the main components of the OMOP-CDM, help organize and standardize medical terminology across various clinical areas within the OMOP framework.

Figure 1. OMOP-CDM²

Since observational databases vary in their purposes and designs, the CDM is adaptable enough to handle different aspects of electronic health records (like Patient Demographic, Conditions, Drug Exposures, Procedures, Measurements etc.) and derive evidence from a wide range of sources. It also develops collaborative research across different data sources while remaining usable for data owners and beneficial for data users. Once a database is transformed into the OMOP-CDM (Figure 2), evidence can be generated using standardized analytical tools. The current version of the CDM is CDM v5.4 (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Overview of all tables in OMOP-CDM^{6,17}

The CDM is viewed as a model that focuses on individuals, which means all other tables holding data related to a patient clinical encounter have a relation to the “Person” table. All the history of medical events can be viewed for each patient. Meanwhile, the tables that hold information about providers and care sites linked to patient events are based on each domain. Different types of Events are organized into Domains, which are kept in Domain-specific tables and fields and are represented by Standard Concepts that are unique to each Domain by OHDSI Standardized Vocabularies.

2.2 Standardized Vocabularies

The Standardized Vocabularies include code sets, terminologies, and classifications required for generating standardized data from various datasets into the OMOP-CDM, and they create a basis for searching, querying, extracting transformed data, and mapping of concepts in observational data analytics systems. The vocabularies are an essential part of the OMOP-CDM and were initially developed with the CDM. Following the conclusion of the OMOP project in November 2013, the OHDSI organization¹⁸ has continued to support the OMOP Standardized Vocabularies. The OHDSI Vocabularies focus on storing data related to individuals for further analysis and evidence generation (secondary use)¹⁹.

As illustrated in Figure 2, the OMOP-CDM standardized vocabulary part uses several data tables to store concepts, vocabularies, and their relationship. The Vocabulary Table contains information about controlled vocabularies in OMOP-CDM, and the Concept Table stores individual clinical entities, such as conditions and medications. Each concept is associated with a specific vocabulary. The “Concept_Relationship” table stores the hierarchies and relations between concepts, and the

“Concept Synonym” table contains alternative designations for concepts to improve the searchability of concepts. The Domain Table organizes concepts into categories, including Conditions and Drugs, while the Source Table correlates source codes with OMOP concepts, aiding in data integration. Collectively, these tables enable efficient querying and analysis of observational data, providing collaborative research efforts and enhancing the reproducibility of studies.

Figure 3. OMOP Standardized Vocabularies entity-relationship diagram - Vocabulary portion of OMOP-CDM²⁰

All clinical events are represented as concepts in OMOP-CDM. These concepts serve as the foundational elements of data records, resulting in a highly normalized structure with few exceptions. The system is designed to be comprehensive, encompassing sufficient concepts to address any events related to a patient’s healthcare encounters, including drugs, conditions, procedures, and administrative aspects like healthcare providers and visits. Each clinical event is represented by a designated Standard Concept²¹. Table 2 illustrates part of the vocabulary used for concept types, including Standard, non-standard, and classification concepts. Several non-

standard concepts may exist in the data sources and are still integral to the vocabulary of some systems and are considered “source concepts”. The non-standard concepts are assigned to standard concepts through the mapping process. Classification concepts, while not Standard and therefore not applicable for data representation, participate in the hierarchy alongside Standard Concepts, enabling their use in hierarchical queries.

Table 2. Part of vocabularies classified based on concept types (Standard/non-standard/classification), 21

Domain	for Standard Concepts	for source concepts	for classification concepts
Condition	SNOMED, ICDO3	SNOMED Veterinary	MedDRA
Procedure	SNOMED, CPT4, HCPCS, ICD10PCS, ICD9Proc, OPCS4	SNOMED Veterinary, HemOnc, NAACCR	None at this point
Measurement	SNOMED, LOINC	SNOMED Veterinary, NAACCR, CPT4, HCPCS, OPCS4, PPI	None at this point
Drug	RxNorm, RxNorm Extension, CVX	HCPCS, CPT4, HemOnc, NAAACCR	ATC
Device	SNOMED	Others, currently not normalized	None at this point
Observation	SNOMED	Others	None at this point
Visit	CMS Place of Service, ABMT, NUCC	SNOMED, HCPCS, CPT4, UB04	None at this point

Maintained as open-source resources, the OHDSI vocabularies promote transparency in their generation processes. OHDSI employs OMOP vocabularies to standardize health data across multiple domains. These key domains include Conditions (e.g., SNOMED CT, ICD-10), Drugs (e.g., RxNorm, ATC), Procedures (e.g., CPT, HCPCS), Measurements (e.g., LOINC for laboratory results), Observations (e.g., SNOMED CT for patient-reported outcomes), and Devices (e.g., FDA device classifications, SNOMED CT for devices). Each domain uses these terminologies to provide consistency and interoperability, enabling large-scale observational research and improving the screening/prediction of healthcare outcomes through a standardized vocabulary framework¹⁰. Table 3 illustrates the domains, OMOP standard vocabularies, classifications, and sources based on the OHDSI vocabularies repository (e.g. Athena²²).

OHDSI has developed a searchable database called Athena²², which serves as a resource for researchers seeking to identify and map codes to OMOP equivalents. Specifically, the Athena tool facilitates the standardized use of medical terminology within the OMOP-CDM by providing researchers with a comprehensive repository of standardized vocabularies. It enables researchers

Table 3. OMOP standardised Vocabulary main domains and vocabularies¹²

Domain	Preferred for Standard	Classification	Source	Abbreviations (No.) and Description
Condition	SNOMED[1], OMOP Extension[2]	MedDRA[3], SMQ[4]	ICD-10[5], ICD-10(CM)[6], ICD-10(CN)[7], ICD-10(GM)[8], ICD-9(CM)[9], KCD7[10], CIM10[11], CIEL[12], HemOnc[13], OPCS4[14], OXMIS[15], PPI[16], Read[17]	1: SNOMED - Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine; 2: OMOP Extension - Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Extension; 3: MedDRA - Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities; 4: SMQ - Standardized MedDRA Queries; 5: ICD-10 - International Classification of Diseases, 10th Revision; 6: ICD-10(CM) - Clinical Modification; 7: ICD-10(CN) - China version; 8: ICD-10(GM) - German Modification; 9: ICD-9(CM) - Clinical Modification; 10: KCD7 - Korean Classification of Diseases 7th edition; 11: CIM10 - Classification Internationale des Maladies, 10th Revision (French); 12: CIEL - Columbia International eHealth Laboratory vocabulary; 13: HemOnc - Hematology-Oncology; 14: OPCS4 - Office of Population Censuses and Surveys Classification of Interventions and Procedures, version 4; 15: OXMIS - Oxford Medical Information System; 16: PPI - Patient Procedure Index; 17: Read - Clinical terminology system
Device	SNOMED[1], HCPCS[18], CPT4[19], ICD10PCS[20], CDT*[21]	SPL[22]	AMIS[23], DA_France[24], EDI[25], dm+d[26], HCPCS[18], CIEL[12], OXMIS[15], OPCS4[14], Nebraska Lexicon[27], Gemscript[28], LPD_Australia[29], Read[17], SUS[30], NCCD[31], LPD_Belgium[32], GGR[33], ICD10PCS[20], ISBT[34], JMDC[35], KDC[36], dm+d[26], NDC[37], AMT[38], OPCS4[14]	18: HCPCS - Healthcare Common Procedure Coding System; 19: CPT4 - Current Procedural Terminology, 4th edition; 20: ICD10PCS - ICD-10 Procedure Coding System; 21: CDT* - Current Dental Terminology; 22: SPL - Structured Product Labeling; 23: AMIS - ??? (Please specify if needed); 24: DA_France - Data Authority France; 25: EDI - Electronic Data Interchange; 26: dm+d - Dictionary of Medicines and Devices (UK); 27: Nebraska Lexicon - Terminology used in Nebraska; 28: Gemscript - ??? (Please specify if needed); 29: LPD_Australia - Medicine database Australia; 30: SUS - System Ushering System (Brazil); 31: NCCD - ??? (Please specify if needed); 32: LPD_Belgium - Medicine database Belgium; 33: GGR - ??? (Please specify if needed); 34: ISBT - International Society of Blood Transfusion; 35: JMDC - Japan Medical Data Center; 36: KDC - Korean Drug Code; 37: NDC - National Drug Code (US); 38: AMT - ??? (Please specify if needed)
Drug	RxNorm[39], RxNorm Extension[40], CVX[41]	ATC[42], EphMRA ATC[43], ETC[44], NDFRT[45], CVX[41], Indication[46], SPL[22]	AMIS[23], LPD_Belgium[32], DA_France[24], GGR[33], ICD10PCS[20], VA Product[47], SNOMED Veterinary[48], Multilex[49], EDI[25], dm+d[26], JMDC[35], NAACCR[50], KDC[36], DPD[51], SNOMED[1], NDC[37], HCPCS[18], CPT4[19], Multum[52], CTD[53], CIEL[12], OXMIS[15], HemOnc[13], GPI[54], AMT[38], VA Class[55], Nebraska Lexicon[27], Gemscript[28], BDPM[56], PPI[16], LPD_Australia[29], GRR[57], Read[17], GCN_SEQNO[58], MeSH[59], SUS[30], NCCD[31]	39: RxNorm - Drug terminology by the US National Library of Medicine; 40: RxNorm Extension - Extended RxNorm; 41: CVX - Vaccine Admin Codes; 42: ATC - Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical classification; 43: EphMRA ATC - European Pharmaceutical Market Research Association ATC; 44: ETC - ??? (Please specify); 45: NDFRT - National Drug File - Reference Terminology; 46: Indication - Medication indication; 47: VA Product - Veterans Affairs Product Code; 48: SNOMED Veterinary - Veterinary extension of SNOMED; 49: Multilex - Drug database; 50: NAACCR - North American Association of Central Cancer Registries; 51: DPD - Drug Product Database; 52: Multum - Drug database; 53: CTD - Comparative Toxicogenomics Database; 54: GPI - Generic Product Identifier; 55: VA Class - Veterans Affairs Drug Classification; 56: BDPM - Base de Données Publique des Médicaments; 57: GRR - ???; 58: GCN_SEQNO - ???; 59: MeSH - Medical Subject Headings
Measurement	LOINC[60], SNOMED[1], OMOP Extension*[2]	LOINC[60], MeDRA[3]	ICD-10(CM)[6], CAP[61], CGI[62], EDI[25], NAACCR[50], JAX[63], ICD-10[5], HCPCS[18], CPT4[19], CIEL[12], OXMIS[15], ClinVar[64], OPCS4[14], Nebraska Lexicon[27], PPI[16], ICD-10(GM)[8], NCI[65], OncoKB[66], Read[17], MeSH[59], ICD-9(CM)[9], SUS[30], KCD7[10], ICD-10(CN)[7], CIM10[11], CIVIC[67], UK Biobank[68]	60: LOINC - Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes; 61: CAP - College of American Pathologists; 62: CGI - ??? (Please specify); 63: JAX - Jackson Laboratory; 64: ClinVar - Clinical Variant Database; 65: NCI - National Cancer Institute Thesaurus; 66: OncoKB - Oncology Knowledge Base; 67: CIVIC - Clinical Interpretation of Variants in Cancer; 68: UK Biobank - Large-scale biomedical database
Observation	SNOMED[1], HCPCS[18], CPT4[19], LOINC[60], OMOP Extension*[2]	LOINC[60], MedDRA[3]	ICD-10(CM)[6], CAP[61], NAACCR[50], ICD-10[5], HCPCS[18], CIEL[12], OXMIS[15], LOINC[60], PCORNet[69], OPCS4[14], Nebraska Lexicon[27], PPI[16], ICD-10(GM)[8], Read[17], ICD-9(CM)[9], SUS[30], KCD7[10], ICD-10(CN)[7], CIM10[11], UK Biobank[68], ICDO3[70]	69: PCORNet - Patient-Centered Outcomes Research Network; 70: ICDO3 - International Classification of Diseases for Oncology, 3rd Edition
Procedure	CPT4[19], SNOMED[1], ICD10PCS[20], ICD9Proc[71], HCPCS[18]	CPT4[19], MedDRA[3]	ICD-10(CM)[6], CCAM[72], EDI[25], NAACCR[50], ICD-10[5], OPS[73], CIEL[12], OXMIS[15], HemOnc[13], OPCS4[14], Nebraska Lexicon[27], ICD-10(GM)[8], Read[17], CDT[21], MeSH[59], ICD-9(CM)[9], MedDRA[3], SUS[30], KCD7[10], ICD9ProcCN[74], ICD-10(CN)[7], CIM10[11]	71: ICD9Proc - ICD-9 Procedure codes; 72: CCAM - Classification Commune des Actes Médicaux; 73: OPS - Operationen- und Prozedurenschlüssel (Germany); 74: ICD9ProcCN - ICD-9 Procedure Codes China

to search for specific conditions, such as gestational diabetes, and retrieve relevant information, including the Domain ID, Concept IDs for related terms, and a visual representation of hierarchical relationships. This repository and hierarchy help researchers to explore the hierarchical structure of concepts, identifying ancestors (e.g., diabetes mellitus during pregnancy) and descendants (e.g., postpartum gestational diabetes).

2.3 Metadata Standards

This section describes the standards related to metadata and data catalogs. At the current state of the project, we have agreed to use the DCAT-AP metadata standard. Other metadata standards and models, including HealthDCAT-AP, Bioschema, DISH, and GAIA-X descriptions, are presented to adjust the base DCAT model for future and advanced IDERHA requirements to share metadata about datasets and related legal and ethical information.

2.3.1 Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT)

DCAT²³ provides the necessary markups for metadata exchange with data catalogs published on the web, facilitating metadata integration and use among data catalogs with standard data models. It consists of standardized RDF-based vocabularies describing datasets, data services, and catalogs, increasing the visibility of web resources. DCAT enables the decentralized publishing of data catalogs and provides mechanisms to query datasets from multiple sites within a federated infrastructure. More recently, DCAT version 2 has supported data services and offered more comprehensive details for describing datasets. It also enhances the relationships between datasets and linking resources. A dataset series class was introduced, representing a collection of related datasets, and alignment with schema.org was included.

Figure 4. DCAT model overview¹⁴

2.3.2 DCAT Application Profile (DCAT-AP)

The DCAT Application Profile²⁴ presents a framework derived from DCAT that provides descriptions of datasets that increase the visibility and discoverability between data portals. This is accomplished by sharing dataset descriptions among various data portals. It facilitates the interoperability and semantic findability of datasets across Europe (although some other extensions of DCAT are used outside Europe). The application profile uses metadata standards and vocabularies to ensure interoperability with other applications covering Europe’s certain requirements. DCAT-AP helps data consumers easily locate datasets using a single point of access.

The dataset's metadata are aggregated in their corresponding data catalog using standardized descriptions and are well documented to increase reusability.

2.3.3 Asset Description Metadata Schema (ADMS)

The Asset Description Metadata Schema (ADMS)²⁵ is a specific version of the Data Catalog Vocabulary (DCAT) for describing Semantic Assets. These assets include reusable metadata, schemas, generic data models, reference data, taxonomies, and vocabularies. While DCAT is developed to establish interoperability among data catalogs, ADMS is used to describe the assets within the catalogs. ADMS uses existing metadata standards, including Dublin Core, DCAT, FOAF, and vCard, to describe semantic assets. ADMS models can be used in federated environments; they are stored in catalog repositories and made available through various distribution methods, including web pages or machine-processable services.

2.3.4 HealthDCAT-AP

HealthDCAT-AP²⁶ is a health-focused extension of the DCAT-AP, designed for sharing information about datasets and catalogues that contain descriptions of datasets and data services in Europe. This profile is maintained by the SEMIC action under the initiative of Interoperable Europe. HealthDCAT-AP introduces a customized RDF format for the needs of electronic health data. One of the main goals of EHDS project is to establish an EU Datasets Catalogue connecting the national catalogues of datasets established by the health data access bodies. Aligned with this strategy, healthDCAT application profile extends the DCAT framework in open data portals across Europe. This standard aligns with the objectives of the EU4Health program. It is also a deliverable of Work Package 6 within the EHDS2 pilot project consortium. HealthDCAT-AP It builds upon the main entities and conformance criteria of DCAT-AP, introducing new properties, cardinalities and vocabularies.

2.3.4 Bioschema

Bioschema is focused on improving the online visibility of life sciences resources (applications, datasets, etc.). It encourages life science professionals to use Schema.org markup on their websites, which allows these resources to be indexed by search engines and other services. Bioschema facilitated interoperability across different sites by consistently improving markup standards for biological information. It increases the findability, integration and analysis of distributed life science data and provides guidelines for marking up various resources, including datasets and catalogs²⁷.

Bioschemas creates new types and properties within Schema.org to accurately describe life science resources, and it defines usage profiles for Schema.org types that specify the essential properties needed for resource description. As one of the ELIXIR²⁸ initiatives (the European Life-sciences Infrastructure for Biological Information), Bioschemas is a key element of their Scientific Programme for 2024-2028. The International Society for Biocuration also recommends using Bioschemas markup to improve the discoverability of resources.

2.3.4 Data Information Sheet (DISH)

The Data Information Sheet (DISH)²⁹ is a tool utilized by ELIXIR to gather information on cohorts and data sets for translational biomedicine projects. These projects frequently involve sensitive data from human participants, necessitating the collection of details regarding data usage limitations and GDPR compliance. Typically, a translational biomedicine project encompasses multiple clinical study sites and may include several cohorts. Data holders are required to complete the DISH before submitting their data to ELIXIR. Information about the study use conditions, restrictions, submission overview, legal representation, study cohort and data categories is gathered.

2.3.5 Gaia-X Self-Description

IDERHA metadata model would be designed inspired by and aligned with metadata models, including Gaia-X Self-Description. “Gaia-X is a decentralized, federated ecosystem designed for the sovereign exchange of data and digital services”³⁰. It aligns with European values and regulations, providing an interoperable infrastructure grounded in shared rules and standards. The Gaia-X Trust Framework and Policy Rules establish the foundation for trust, compliance, and semantic interoperability. The Gaia-X Conceptual Model represents all entities within the Gaia-X framework and their interrelationships. The primary entities include those categorized as “provider,” “service offering,” and “resource.” A provider is defined as a participant within Gaia-X who offers services and manages resources. A service offering describes a digital service available for procurement and may consist of various resources or depend on other offerings from third-party providers. A resource serves as a fundamental component of a service offering that is not directly available for order.

In the Gaia-X framework, all providers must articulate their identities and service offerings through standardized, machine-readable metadata referred to as Self-Descriptions³¹. Self-Description comprises a set of assertions regarding the characteristics of a provider, service offering, or resource. The vocabulary used to express these assertions is termed the Self-Description Schema, which defines a hierarchical structure of classes corresponding to the Conceptual Model and elaborates further in the subsequent taxonomy. For each class, a collection of attributes is specified, detailing the name, datatype, and, where applicable, references to underlying standards as outlined by the W3C.

2.3.6 Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL)

The Open Digital Rights Language (ODRL)³² provides an expression language for describing policy, usage of content, and services. It has its encoding model, vocabulary, and data model. It serves as a standard language for defining terms and conditions related to assets, including a core set of semantics that address rights holders and permissible uses. By enhancing traditional rights management standards, ODRL introduces digital equivalents and supports the innovative and transparent use of digital resources in various domains, such as electronic publications, digital images, audio, films, educational materials, software, and other digital creations. This framework is designed to facilitate new services made possible by the digital nature of online assets and can also be applied in physical contexts to automate rights management processes.

ODRL provides specifications for the semantics involved in expressing rights and includes a data dictionary for defining its elements. Rightthe vocabulary isigned specifically to certain asset formats or applied across multiple manifestations of the same asset. It is versatile enough to be implemented in both trusted and untrusted systems, with the potential for additional semantics to be integrated for third-party value-added services, backed by supplementary data dictionaries.

2.4 Imaging Data

2.4.1 Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM)

The DICOM standard defines the essential data formats for exchanging medical image data³³. As one of the most widely adopted healthcare standards, it ensures data integrity and quality for clinical applications³⁴. This standard is embedded in nearly all imaging devices, including X-ray, MRI, and CT machines. It covers several medical specialties (radiology, dentistry, cardiology, ophthalmology, and radiotherapy). The International Organization for Standardization recognizes DICOM as ISO 2052:2017³⁵.

The DICOM Standard is one of the famous standards in the healthcare industry, specifically focusing on the interoperability of medical image information among healthcare systems and medical devices. DICOM was mainly developed to support medical diagnostics in radiology, dentistry, pathology, cardiology, ophthalmology, and interventional procedures. However, it should also cover other domains to provide the full scope of medical informatics standards. Additionally, DICOM contains several data items related to images and some items not directly related to the image. This information is further used and exchanged in diverse medical and research settings.

2.4.2 OMOP-CDM Imaging Extension

In 2021, the OHDSI community united research and observational health scientists familiar with OMOP-CDM as the Medical Imaging Working Group (MI WG)⁷. The primary clinical focus of the group is on the longitudinal monitoring of various lung nodules, highlighting crucial attributes such as location, size of the nodule, shape, CT parameters, density, and other phenotypic traits. To aid this work, they have created two tables, `Image_occurrence` and `Image_feature`, extensions to the OMOP-CDM, allowing for the standardized documentation of complex medical imaging events and characteristics.

The OMOP-CDM Medical Imaging extension is intended to include not just radiological exams but also all DICOM-based studies in different specialties, such as pathology and ophthalmology. This model establishes a framework for integrating DICOM into the OMOP-CDM. The initiative seeks to combine image data with clinical data extracted from electronic health records in a standardized manner, thus enhancing advanced outcome research. As part of this initiative, the team intends to map DICOM vocabulary to OMOP concepts. All Images (DICOM objects) contain pixel data along with a header that includes attributes identifying the device parameters and modality information.

2.4.3 Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative (NifTI)

NifTI standard is used to store imaging data, especially from brain scans taken with Magnetic Resonance Imaging (MRI). NifTI is an open file format that aims to provide support, training, and research to help develop and enhance neuroimaging tools. The goals of this project are to improve the tools used in neuroimaging research and to share information about these tools. This project is sponsored by the National Institute of Mental Health and the National Institute of Neurological Disorders and Stroke³⁶. It includes specifications that relate voxel indices (i, j, k) to locations spatial information (x, y, z), as well as codes to indicate spatio-temporal slice ordering specifically for functional MRI (fMRI). NifTI supports a wide range of data types, from 8 to 128 bits, and provides a standardized method for storing vector-valued datasets across one to four-dimensional domains.

In contrast to DICOM standard, which can be resource-intensive and complex to implement, NifTI offers a more streamlined and minimalistic alternative. Because of the simplicity it has been widely applied in related to neuroimaging, NifTI is supported by community-developed C libraries that facilitate reading and writing NifTI files without necessitating extensive re-implementation efforts. NifTI uses images with up to seven dimensions, allowing for greater flexibility in representing complex data structures, including spatial orientation information that reduces the likelihood of errors in left-right mapping³⁷.

2.5 Molecular Genetics and Biology data

The IMI eTRIKS project has published the eTRIKS Starter Pack¹⁵. It thoroughly overviews biomedical data standards and specifies recommendations appropriate for each research initiative. This document is mainly designed for data managers and project leaders. The documents in the Standards Starter Pack were shared with all IMI projects to encourage uniformity in data management and to highlight the benefits of using consistent standards in translational research efforts. The following standards provide recommendations for managing translational data encompassing biological and genomic information. These initiatives collectively aim to standardize data practices, facilitating improved research outcomes in the field of translational medicine.

In this section, we present the data standards that we agreed to use in the IDERHA project for molecular biology and genetic data.

2.5.1 CDISC SDTM

The Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium (CDISC) establishes pharmaceutical data standards. CDISC is a global non-profit organization. The Study Data Tabulation Model (SDTM)³⁸ outlines a standardized framework for tabulating both human and non-clinical study data for official submission to official authorities (similar to the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA)). SDTM standardizes the organization and formatting of data, which helps streamline data integration and analysis and facilitates data sharing. With CDISC SDTM, data collection can be standardized throughout, featuring established domain names, a uniform structure for each domain, standardized variables, and consistent naming conventions for datasets.

This ensures that all data collected across studies can be easily identified, allowing regulators to review it more quickly and making the overall process significantly more efficient.

2.5.2 Genomic-CDM (G-CDM)

The Genomic-CDM (G-CDM) standard enhances the OMOP-CDM to effectively manage clinical sequencing data through a structured database framework³⁹. To integrate genomic related data within the OMOP-CDM, specific data about patients with Next Generation Sequencing (NGS) information was organized into data entities. These included Person, Condition_Occurrence (diagnosis), Procedure_Occurrence, Specimen, and Care_Site. The G-CDM further advanced the model by incorporating additional entities related to sequencing data. One entity documents the tests, sequencing devices, analytical tools, and related databases. Another entity enumerates the genes targeted by the genomic test, adhering to the standardized gene symbols established by the Human Genome Organization Gene Nomenclature Committee (HGNC). Additionally, an entity provided descriptive information about the variants associated with the target genes. Finally, another entity detailed each variant and its clinical interpretation⁴⁰. This standard is developed under the supervision of OHDSI Oncology working group⁶. The OHDSI Oncology Working Group aims to establish a foundation for representing cancer data within the OMOP-CDM, ensuring the necessary levels of granularity and abstraction to support observational cancer research. Similarly, the Oncology CDM Extension of the OMOP-CDM seeks to fulfill this objective. It is noteworthy that oncology support within OMOP is currently an ongoing endeavor.

2.5.3 GA4GH Framework

The Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH)⁴¹ facilitates the exchange of genomic and clinical data in biomedical practices using federated infrastructures and data standardization. seeks to speed up biomedical progress by facilitating the responsible exchange of clinical and genomic information using both standardized data aggregation and federated infrastructure. GA4GH is actively working on the technical details and policies that provide interoperability between datasets for genomic research in a federated environment.

GA4GH has focused on keeping and improving standard file formats of genomic data (like SAM, BAM, CRAM, VCF/BCF), representing and interpreting individual genetic variants (VRS, VA), and sharing individual health data (Phenopackets). These elements are crucial for integrating genomics into healthcare systems, especially in clinical labs that share genomic data and genetic testing results. helping data-sharing projects that show the benefits of collaboration. To help health outcome prediction processes, GA4GH provides instructions for distributing individuals' clinical and genomic data. It applies to data that donors (or their legal representatives) have agreed to share or that has been approved for use by the right authorities, following ethical guidelines.

GA4GH has previously established two standards for biomedical data discovery: Beacon⁴², which focuses on the discovery of genomic variants, and Matchmaker⁴³, designed for identifying subjects with specific genomic and phenotypic characteristics. These standards have been integrated into federated networks, achieving success independently while sharing many similarities. Developing searchable, federated networks applicable to various genomics and health scenarios. The Beacon protocol outlines the programming interface (API) necessary for implementing individual beacon

resources, which utilize the Beacon API often enhanced with a user interface to facilitate the discovery of genomic data. The second version of the Beacon protocol (v2) was accepted as a GA4GH standard in Spring 2022 and is founded on a two-part concept: the Beacon Framework and the Beacon Model. schema and message format of the API, and may be referred to as the Framework. In contrast, the Beacon Model encompasses components such as individual or biosamples and may be referred to as the Model.

2.6 Socioeconomic Data

The European Union has made strong efforts to bring together socioeconomic data to support research on living conditions and quality of life. One important initiative is the European Socio-Economic Classification (ESeC)⁴⁴, developed under the “Citizens and Governance in a Knowledge-Based Society” programme. This classification system helps organize information about individuals based on their occupation and employment status.

On the other hand, the HL7 FHIR Gravity Project⁴⁵ developed a standardized way to share information about social factors that influence health, known as Social Determinants of Health (SDOH). Its primary objective is to create data and exchange standards that accurately represent SDOH data at the patient level across four main health-related activities. These include aspects such as housing, income, and access to food. This information is used in clinical settings to assist with screening, diagnosis, treatment planning, and monitoring progress. It also involves identifying common data elements and their corresponding value sets to support these use cases. Furthermore, the project will provide recommendations on the optimal methods for capturing and organizing these data elements to enable interoperable electronic exchange and aggregation.

2.7 Environmental Data

The European Environment Agency (EEA) establishes guidelines for the transparent sharing of environmental data. The European Environment Information and Observation Network (Eionet) acts as a collaborative network under the EEA's supervision. The EEA is responsible for developing Eionet and coordinating its activities with National Focal Points (NFPs) in 38 countries. Each NFP is the main contact point for running the activities related to EEA's programs. The European Union established the Infrastructure for Spatial Information in the European Community (INSPIRE) to facilitate the sharing and use of spatial data across member states. INSPIRE provides instructions to produce, receive, manage, and update spatial datasets for members. INSPIRE is based on the spatial information infrastructures established and operated by EU member states, categorizing datasets under 34 spatial data themes. INSPIRE was formally adopted through a directive by the European Parliament and the Council of the European Union on March 14, 2007. It facilitates the interoperability of spatial data and services across Europe, promising that data from different countries can be easily integrated.

The INSPIRE Metadata Implementing Rules are based on the technical guidelines of EN ISO 19115, EN ISO 19119 , and ISO 19136 . ISO 19119:2016. Geographic Information specifies the

requirements for creating platform-neutral and platform-specific service specifications. This allows a service to be defined independently of various underlying distributed computing platforms. It also outlines the process for mapping platform-neutral specifications to platform-specific ones, ensuring that service implementations are compliant and interoperable. Moreover, it establishes a classification system for geographic services based on a service taxonomy related to architectural areas. It also permits categorization from the perspective of the service's usage life cycle, as well as through domain-specific and user-defined taxonomies, thereby facilitating the easier publication and Discovery of services. On the other hand, ISO 19115-1 Geographic Information — metadata. defines the schema necessary for describing geographic information and services through metadata. It includes details about identification, extent, quality, spatial and temporal aspects, content, spatial reference, portrayal, distribution, and other characteristics of digital geographic data and services.

ISO 19136-1:2020 defines the Geography Markup Language (GML) as an XML encoding that adheres to ISO 19118 for the transport and storage of geographic information. This information is modeled according to the conceptual framework outlined in the ISO 19100 series of International Standards, encompassing both the spatial and non-spatial characteristics of geographic features. The document describes the XML syntax and mechanisms that establish an open, vendor-neutral framework for describing geospatial application schemas intended for the transport and storage of geographic information in XML. It aids in detailing geospatial application schemas tailored for specialized domains and information communities and enhances the capacity of organizations to share these schemas and the information they encapsulate.

2.8 Security and Privacy Standards for Personal Health Data (PHD)

The Regulation on Electronic Identification, Authentication, and Trust Services (eIDAS) has successfully established a regulatory framework within the European Union. It tries to enhance confidence in cross-border electronic transactions while improving the efficacy of online services and e-commerce platforms. This regulation specifically addresses electronic identification (eID) and trust service providers, to improve utilization of trust services and eID across EU members. A fundamental component of the eIDAS Regulation is the establishment of mutual recognition for eIDs issued by EU member states. This mutual recognition facilitates secure electronic transactions by ensuring that an eID issued in one member state is recognized and accepted in all others. Mutual recognition becomes mandatory for eIDs that satisfy certain assurance levels, thereby simplifying cross-border interactions and enhancing trust in online services⁴⁶.

Additionally, the adherence to ISO 27001/2 upholds best practice standards. This international standard provides instructions for organizations of all sizes in creating, maintaining, and improving an information security management system, ensuring that risks related to data security are effectively managed and aligned with recognized best practices⁴⁷.

The GA4GH Steering Committee has endorsed the GA4GH Passports and Authentication & Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) specifications⁴⁸ created by the GA4GH Data Use & Researcher Identities (DURI) and Data Security Work Streams. These two standards work together to verify a researcher's digital identity and automate their access to requested genomic datasets. These standards enhance efficiency by facilitating the automation of the data access process. The GA4GH Passport Standard⁴⁹ establishes a digital identity that provides the roles and data access

rights of individual users, referred to as "visas." These visas are granted by data stewards, which include data access committees (DACs) connected to public databases, overseeing the quality, integrity, and access protocols of datasets for managing human biomedical data. Passports aid in overseeing data access rights across various systems by employing visas that communicate a data user's digital identity and permissions among different organizations, tools, environments, and services. The AAI establishes a federated method of granting access to individuals based on the authentication of their identity. The GA4GH AAI can be used for datasets in different domains (domain agnostic). While AAI establishes the means for user authentication and conveys claims about their identity, GA4GH Passports offers the data format that allows those claims to relate to dataset permissions, roles, and resources. Using the AAI access token, the GA4GH Passport maps access to data by a researcher's digital identity and permissions across different companies, tools, and environments.

2.9 Standards for Communication of Patient Reported Experience/Outcome Measures Data

Patient Reported Outcomes (PROs) include any health information shared directly by the patient, without input from doctors or other professionals. These outcomes can be measured in clear terms, like the severity of symptoms or the condition of a disease or compared to previous measurements. Patient Reported Outcome Measures (PROMs) help improve patient care, support shared decision-making, encourage patients to manage their own health, aid in care planning, assist in setting and achieving goals, and contribute to research focused on patient-centered outcomes. The Patient Reported Outcomes (PRO) FHIR Implementation Guide (IG)⁵⁰ emphasizes the electronic collection and sharing of patient-reported outcome data using the FHIR standard. This collected data is accessible to both healthcare providers and approved researchers.

Parts of FHIR PRO which is covered by OMOP-CDM could be mapped into OMOP including biometric information, medical history, symptoms, treatment history, and lifestyle choices. This information may be recorded by patients themselves, family members, caregivers, or through medical devices. Such data can be integrated utilizing the OMOP-CDM.

Additionally, data produced by patient wearables and other monitoring devices necessitate adherence to standards such as ISO/IEEE 11073 to ensure compatibility with medical devices for effective data exchange. Currently, The ISO/IEEE 11073 targets point-of-care (PoC) medical device communication, and an architecture for service-oriented distributed PoC medical devices and medical IT systems is defined. This standard specifies the binding of the Participant, Discovery, and Communication Model, as defined in IEEE Std 11073-1020, to the profile for transport over Web Services as outlined in IEEE Std 11073-20702⁵¹.

2.10 Data Quality and Performance Measurement

The IDERHA Data Quality (DQ) framework is based on recent literature that identifies key data quality dimensions crucial for secondary use, particularly in areas such as decision-making and real-world evidence generation. This framework, consisting of nine data quality dimensions, has been designed to ensure that health data meets the necessary standards required for these

applications. It draws upon previous frameworks established by leading institutions, including the European Medicines Agency (EMA)⁵² and the Towards the European Health Data Space (TEHDAS) initiative⁵³. These efforts provide foundational guidelines for ensuring data quality in alignment with the goals of the European Health Data Space (EHDS) for secondary use⁵⁴.

Our starting point in the IDERHA DQ framework involves using dimensions that may differ in terminology from those employed by the EHDS. However, the definitions of these dimensions align closely with key aspects recognized by EHDS, ensuring compatibility in their underlying principles. While maintaining this alignment, the IDERHA framework also seeks to extend the EHDS recommendations by introducing additional elements tailored to the specific needs of secondary data use, such as AI-driven decision-making. This approach allows us to build on the solid foundation laid by the EHDS while enhancing its scope to offer a more comprehensive framework for health data quality, especially in federated data environments.

To fully understand whether data is fit for purpose in terms of quality, it is essential to have insights and results throughout the entire data lifecycle, from the primary source to data transformation and ultimately to its secondary use. Although many data standards currently exist, they often focus on evaluating the quality of data at specific stages within the lifecycle, such as data collection (e.g. technical level assessment of the EHR). These standards rarely cover the entire lifecycle. This fragmented approach leaves critical gaps in ensuring that data maintains high quality and reliability across all stages, from primary collection to transformation and ultimately to secondary use.

For example, dataset-specific standards, such as ISO/IEC 25012⁵⁵ or EHR Data Quality Assessment Tools⁵⁶, concentrate on assessing isolated characteristics of data like completeness and consistency. Similarly, the METRIC framework is addressing “fit for purpose” specifically for training AI models⁵⁷. In contrast, lifecycle-based standards provide a more governance perspective, ensuring long-term quality management without necessarily offering an in-depth analysis of the dataset itself at each stage. For example, ISO/IEC 8000⁵⁸ emphasizes the continuous management of data quality across the entire lifecycle. Similarly, Shah et al. discussed mitigating AI biases throughout the entire life cycle⁵⁹. Or the Data Quality Dashboard (DQD) developed by OHDSI/OMOP⁶⁰, providing insights to maintain data quality throughout data mapping. On the other hand, while the FAIR principles enhance the reuse of data by focusing on its discoverability and interoperability, they do not explicitly assess whether the intrinsic quality of the data is fit for purpose. In other words, the FAIR principles⁵¹ emphasize the accessibility and usability of data but do not guarantee that the underlying data itself meets the necessary data quality standards for specific applications (e.g. decision-making).

The challenge is that while many standards focus on either datasets or the lifecycle, few frameworks comprehensively cover both aspects. This creates gaps in ensuring the data's consistency and quality across its entire journey. To address this gap, the IDERHA DQ framework will be designed to cover both dataset-specific and lifecycle-based dimensions, with a particular focus on data quality for AI training. This data quality framework is part of the IDERHA task deliverables (D4.2).

2.11 Data Sharing Standards for AI

There are two main standards that are relevant to IDERHA in the field of AI and EHR data analysis. The standard Open Neural Network Exchange (ONNX) is an open format dedicated to

represent neural network-based models⁶¹. ONNX essentially represents an interoperability layer between different AI frameworks and tools. For instance, a model created with the PyTorch framework can easily be used in TensorFlow or other AI frameworks. Hence, it facilitates the deployment of AI models across various platforms. In this way, this standard promotes the sharing and collaboration of AI models, improving accessibility and innovation in research.

The Medical Event Data Standard (MEDS) is a data schema intended for representing medical events derived from EHR data^{62,63}. Medical events refer to significant occurrences related to patient care within the healthcare system. They encompass a wide range of aspects, including diagnoses, which are the identification of medical conditions based on clinical observations and tests, and procedures, which are medical actions performed on patients, such as surgeries or therapies. Additionally, medications and lab reporting results of patients also fall under this category. The standard provides a row-based data schema, where each row represents a single observation with time dimension for a single patient. Hence, each row contains a subject identifier (anonymized or pseudonymized identifier), a time point at which the observation was made (such as hospital visit date), a code and its value providing the observation information (such as a specific medication). Furthermore, MEDS is specifically designed for processing EHR data with transformer-based foundation models, that utilize the deep learning paradigm of pre-training and fine-tuning.

One of the primary objectives of the core IDERHA infrastructure is to facilitate federated exploratory data analysis and federated machine learning (FML) for researchers. IDERHA is designed to support FML frameworks that will be integrated with various components, including those responsible for managing user access and data.

On the other hand, the standard ISO/IEC 42001:2023⁶⁴ establishes a framework for artificial intelligence (AI) risk management, providing specifications for AI Risk Management Systems. It emphasizes the importance of people, processes, and technology in mitigating both internal and external threats. The standard delineates several objectives and controls, including fairness, security, safety, privacy, robustness, transparency, accountability, availability, maintainability, quality of training data, and the necessity for AI expertise.

3. Compliance with FAIR principles

The FAIR principles constitute a comprehensive framework aimed at enhancing the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability of research data. These guidelines are intended to facilitate the efficient sharing and reuse of data by both human users and automated systems, thereby advancing scientific discovery and innovation. Within this context, the Observational Health Data Sciences and Informatics (OHDSI) initiative's OMOP Common Data Model (CDM) promotes data findability through the use of standardized vocabularies and globally unique concept identifiers. In parallel, the IDERHA project reinforces this objective by implementing metadata standards such as DCAT-AP and HealthDCAT-AP. It maintains federated catalogs encompassing

datasets, metadata, and algorithms, each tagged with persistent identifiers to support seamless discovery across distributed platforms. In terms of accessibility, IDERHA integrates dedicated services to ensure secure access and compliance with regulatory frameworks. It employs mechanisms such as eIDAS and Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure (AAI) for identity verification and access control. Furthermore, data privacy and protection are upheld through a structured governance model aligned with relevant legal requirements. Regarding interoperability, the OMOP CDM demonstrates robust capabilities within clinical and observational health domains and accommodates extensions to represent a broader range of data types. IDERHA complements this by adopting standardized metadata models such as DCAT and by utilizing mapping tools to harmonize non-OMOP data with the OMOP structure. A comprehensive platform-wide strategy is currently under development to standardize the application of OMOP extensions and ensure coherence. With respect to reusability, OMOP fosters this dimension through its standardized data schemas, common vocabularies, and a collaborative community that promotes best practices. While it encourages documentation of data provenance, extract-transform-load (ETL) processes, and versioning, these practices remain community-driven and are not enforced by the model itself. To address this, IDERHA adopts the HealthDCAT metadata standard, which explicitly includes fields for capturing data provenance, licensing information, and detailed descriptions of ETL and harmonization procedures.

4. IDERHA Interoperability and Data Exchange

4.1 FHIR to OMOP Data Transfer

Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) is a standard established by Health Level Seven International (HL7) designed for the electronic exchange of healthcare information⁶⁵. The healthcare sector is increasingly adopting this advanced framework to enhance interoperability. EHRs capture patient information in various formats (such as medications and clinical encounters), and FHIR facilitates the standardized representation and sharing of this information among healthcare providers and organizations, irrespective of the local EHR systems' data representation or storage methods. FHIR synthesizes the most effective elements from prior standards into a unified specification, while also being adaptable enough to accommodate a diverse range of use cases within the healthcare ecosystem. At its foundation, FHIR comprises two main components including Resources and APIs. Resources refer to a set of information models that provide the data elements, constraints, and relationships pertinent to the primary "business objects" in healthcare. From the perspective of model-driven architecture, FHIR resources can be conceptually linked to a physical model represented in XML or JSON. APIs are a set of clearly defined interfaces that enable interoperability between applications. While not mandatory, the FHIR specification primarily targets RESTful interfaces for API implementation.

Figure 5. HL7 FHIRFramework⁴

FHIR is primarily applied in various European-level projects focusing on healthcare interoperability, data exchange, and patient-centered care. Projects like MyHealth@EU allow citizens to access their health data across EU countries, while OpenNCP focuses on establishing a network for patient data exchange. Additionally, the European Committee for Standardization’s Technical Committee for Health Informatics (CEN/TC 251) incorporates FHIR into European health information standards. Overall, FHIR plays an important role in providing resources for secondary use.

Currently, most IHE profiles⁸ use the FHIR standard, and each profile supports a clinical or operational domain with its specification. Several profiles have already been tested and published in different domains, including cardiology, dentistry, devices, endoscopy, pathology, pharmacy, etc.

The FHIR and its broader user community are making significant progress in the targeted application of the FHIR standard across various critical domains. Their developers primarily aim

to provide a platform that facilitates the lossless exchange of data, knowledge, and other health artifacts through its extensive array of FHIR resources and compliant APIs. In contrast, the OMOP-CDM is specifically designed to store observational data that is optimized for research analytics and is intended for use by the OHDSI community, which employs OMOP-compliant tools to foster novel research methodologies and discoveries that enhance health outcomes.

HL7 FHIR Accelerator Vulcan⁶⁶ provides a reliable framework for transforming data between FHIR and OMOP which facilitates the broader application of observational data within research systems, allowing for FHIR API access to OMOP databases and enabling data on FHIR servers to populate OMOP instances. It enhances the interoperability of health data, seamlessly integrating clinical and translational research with clinical care to alleviate burdens, promote learning health systems, and ultimately improve patient lives. By establishing a standardized set of transformations between OMOP and FHIR, organizations worldwide can harness both the interoperability capabilities offered by FHIR's API and the advanced analytical methods and tools developed by OHDSI. In turn, it will support the generation of transformed data that is both comparable and consistent, thereby enhancing data reliability, knowledge artifact generation, and the reproducibility of research outcomes⁶⁷.

4.2 CDISC to OMOP Transformer

The Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium (CDISC) Foundational Standards provide a robust framework of guidelines that support both clinical and non-clinical research activities. These standards focus on key principles for defining data standards and include models, domains, and specifications for data representation. The Study Data Tabulation Model (SDTM) Implementation Guide for Medical Devices (SDTMIG-MD) sets data standards specifically for information related to medical devices in clinical research. Meanwhile, the Analysis Dataset Model (ADaM⁶⁸) Implementation Guide for Medical Devices (ADaMIG-MD) details data structures tailored to meet the statistical analysis needs commonly associated with clinical trials involving medical devices.

The OHDSI initiative has proposed a framework for the advanced transformation of CDISC SDTM datasets into the OMOP-CDM⁶⁹. This project, currently under development, aims to enhance the CDM to better support clinical data. Team members have engaged in asynchronous collaboration to devise strategies for selecting the most appropriate standard concepts. The conversion and mapping were thoroughly discussed during meetings to achieve consensus. As a result, they established agreement on several conventions and developed comprehensive mapping guidelines for the extraction, transformation, and loading (ETL) of CDISC SDTM data into the OMOP-CDM. Through this process, the OMOP-CDM becomes more accessible and enriched compared to the original SDTM data, facilitated by imputation and the derivation of information from multiple sources⁶³.

4.3 Schema Validation

In IDERHA, we require schema validation tools to validate the schema, relationships, conditional dependencies, business rules, and vocabularies specified for the project concerning all the data

stored in compliance with a specific data standard. Schematron is a rule-based language for XML document validation and is an international ISO standard (ISO/IEC 19757-3:2020 - Rule-based validation using Schematron). The Schematron schema language differs from most other XML schema languages in that it is rule-based and uses path expressions instead of grammars. This means that rather than creating a grammar for an XML document, a Schematron schema makes assertions applied to a specific context within the document. During schema validation, the validator ensures that the schema's structure is valid and free of duplicate keys. It also checks that the required tables and columns exist with the correct types, foreign key relations, and required fields, as well as vocabulary validation. Additionally, Jsontron is a Schematron-based JSON (JavaScript Object Notation) semantic rule engine that validates the pattern, phase, rule, and context of a JSON file.

5. Summary of IDERHA Data Standards and Recommendations

Table 4 below presents a summary of the IDERHA data standards established through the agreed-upon standard selection process. Additionally, it outlines the recommended standards and guidelines for each of the primary state-of-the-art topics.

Table 4. Summary of recommended standards categorized by the subject of the application

Subject/Application	Standards and useful/ established resources
Observational and Clinical Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership Common Data Model (OMOP-CDM)
Terminology and Vocabulary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OMOP Standardized Vocabularies
Metadata	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DCAT Application Profile (DCAT-AP) • HealthDCAT-AP • DISH • Bioschema • DCAT Asset Description Metadata Schema (ADMS) • Gaia X Self-Description • ORDL
Imaging Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OMOP-CDM Imaging Extension • Digital Imaging and Communications in Medicine (DICOM) • Neuroimaging Informatics Technology Initiative (NIFTI)
Molecular Genetics and Biology data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Genomic-CDM (G-CDM) • Clinical Data Interchange Standards Consortium (CDISC)-Study Data Tabulation Model (SDTM) • GA4GH
Socioeconomic Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HL7 Gravity • European Socio-Economic Classification (ESeC)
Environmental Data	INSPIRE <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO 19115-1:2014 Geographic information—Metadata

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ISO 19119:2016 Geographic information—Services • ISO 19136-1:2020 Geographic information—Geography Markup Language (GML)
Standards for Communication of Patient Reported Experience/Outcome Measures Data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patient Reported Outcomes (PRO) FHIR IG • ISO/IEEE 11073-10201:2020 Health informatics—Device interoperability, Part 10201: Point-of-care medical device communication — Domain information model
Data Quality and Performance Measurement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IDERHA Data Quality (DQ) framework
Data sharing standards for AI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Open Neural Network Exchange (ONYX) • Medical Event Data Standard (MEDS) • ISO/IEC 42001:2023 Information technology—Artificial intelligence—Management system • ISO/AWI 24051-2 Medical laboratories — Part 2: Digital pathology and artificial intelligence (AI)-based image analysis • ISO/IEC 22989 - Information technology — Artificial intelligence — Artificial intelligence concepts and terminology
Security and Privacy Standards for Personal Health Data (PHD)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Equivalent National Legislation (eIDAS) • ISO/IEC 27001:2022 Information security, cybersecurity and privacy protection—Information security management systems—Requirements • GA4GH Passport and AAI

Annex 1. Sample Use Case: Personalized LC Risk Assessment

This section provides an overview of a primary use case associated with the research objectives of the IDERHA initiative, with a particular focus on the standards and guidelines implemented at each stage of the system's data flow. The initiative aims to enhance the integration and utilization of lung cancer (LC) patient data sourced from a variety of entities, including hospitals, laboratories, research institutions, and citizen applications. The patient data collected from diverse sources may exist in multiple formats and employ various terminologies (Figure 6). Common data standards include FHIR, HL7 V3, DICOM, CDISC SDTM, and other proprietary internal data models. This variability presents challenges in ensuring interoperability and consistency across datasets. To address these challenges, data components that align with the OMOP-CDM will undergo a systematic transformation into their corresponding OMOP representations. For instance, FHIR data can be converted to OMOP-CDM using HL7 Vulcan, which facilitates the integration of healthcare data across different systems. Imaging data will be adapted to fit the OMOP Imaging extension, allowing for a standardized approach to managing imaging-related information. Additionally, CDISC SDTM data can be transformed into OMOP format utilizing a specialized CDISC to OMOP converter.

Figure 6 IDERHA potential data sources, flow, and conversion to OMOP-CDM in a sample federated LC risk assessment environment

It is important to note that certain datasets may currently lack a corresponding OMOP data model. For instance, socioeconomic data is agreed to be transmitted through the HL7 Gravity data

standard, which focuses on social determinants of health. Furthermore, patient-reported outcomes collected via citizen applications could be shared through HL7 FHIR PRO protocols or be in OMOP-CDM in advance, enabling patients to contribute valuable insights regarding their health experiences. Each segment of lung cancer patient data may originate from any of the aforementioned sources, and these datasets will be integrated and disseminated through the federated nodes of the IDERHA framework. Each federated node possesses the capability to share metadata about their datasets by the DCAT standard. Although the main standard for building our metadata model is DCAT, the model will further be extended based on HealthDCAT-AP and GAIA-X Description. This shared metadata will be aggregated and managed by the centralized node of IDERHA, which will play a crucial role in facilitating federated artificial intelligence processing. Data harmonization and quality control tools can serve both each federated node and the central node in terms of data curation and integration of different OMOP vocabulary and terminologies and data quality control. Figure 5 demonstrates the diverse data sources and potential centers that function as repositories for lung cancer patient information, emphasizing the interconnectivity of these entities in fostering a comprehensive understanding of lung cancer data within the IDERHA framework.

Each federated node or the central node can utilize the OHDSI USAGI tool to assist in the manual creation of code mappings. It offers suggested mappings based on the textual similarity of code descriptions. If the automated suggestions are inaccurate, users can search for the correct target concepts. Ultimately, users can approve mappings for use in the ETL process. To prepare for the ETL of longitudinal healthcare databases into the OMOP-CDM, White Rabbit can be applied to scan the data and generate a report with all the necessary information to start designing the ETL. Its primary function is to examine the source data, providing detailed insights into the tables, fields, and values present. This report can serve as a reference for designing the ETL, especially when used alongside the Rabbit-In-a-Hat tool. Unlike standard data profiling tools, White Rabbit aims to prevent the display of personally identifiable information (PII) in the generated output file. Users can employ the OHDSI Achilles tool at each federated node or the central node for the characterization, quality assessment, and visualization of observational health databases based on the OMOP-CDP. Meanwhile, the DATA QUALITY DASHBOARD (DQD) applies a standardized data quality assessment terminology to data formatted in the OMOP-CDM. While ACHILLES conducts characterization analyses to provide a comprehensive visual understanding of a CDM instance, the DQD examines data table by table and field by field to quantify the number of records in the CDM that do not meet specified criteria. Technical specifications regarding the architecture and infrastructure are documented in the materials delivered by the IDERHA “Infrastructure and tools for the integration of data” work package. Furthermore, information about the implementation of federated AI algorithms within IDERHA is available in the documents provided by IDERHA in the “Development of AI/ML tools and applications to data” work package.

Annex 2. Data Harmonization Tools

In this section, we outline the tools identified for data preparation tasks, aimed at organizing data to ensure its readiness for use within the IDERHA federated environment. This data is intended for application in artificial intelligence algorithms and other secondary use cases associated with the project. The identified tools have been categorized according to their functionalities, including data ingestion and curation, interoperability and data exchange, data analytics, vocabulary and metadata repositories, and data quality assessment (Table 6). A summary of these identified tools is presented in the table below. The identification of harmonization tools for IDERHA-ready data is a component of Task 4.4 of the project.

We should consider that in this section, we will present the relevant tools for data harmonization; however, we do not have any obligations or assumptions regarding the output of these tools and their use in relation to personal data and GDPR.

Table 6. Data Harmonization Tools/Platforms, URL, and description

	Tool/Platform Name	Documentation URL	Description
Data ingestion/Curation	White Rabbit	https://github.com/OHDSI/WhiteRabbit	Provides the ETL processes for longitudinal healthcare databases transitioning into the OMOP-CDM. Scans the source data, yielding detailed insights into the tables, fields, and corresponding values present within each field. The result of the ETL process can be presented in a graphical user interface using Rabbit-In-a-Hat.
	Rabbit-In-a-Hat	https://ohdsi.github.io/WhiteRabbit/RabbitInAHat.html	Rabbit-In-a-Hat used with White Rabbit to provide a graphical interface for to display the read by White Rabbit
	Usagi	https://www.ohdsi.org/analytic-tools/usagi/	Mapping codes from source systems to the standard terminologies found in the OMOP Vocabulary. Automatically generating an initial mapping based on similarities. Interactive review and correction of the initial mappings.
	ETL-CDMBuilder	https://github.com/OHDSI/ETL-CDMBuilder	A tool to transform observation databases into OMOP-CDM(ETL tool).
	Open Refine	https://github.com/OpenRefine/OpenRefine	Visualize and manipulate large volumes of data simultaneously. useful for exploring, cleaning, and linking extensive datasets. facilitates data transformation by converting values into different formats and normalizing or denormalizing data
	Pentaho Kettle	https://github.com/pentaho/pentaho-kettle	ETL capabilities to integrate a diverse range of data sources, including relational databases, enterprise applications, files, and big data serves as the data integration component of the Pentaho

			Business Analytics suite, which also encompasses data preparation and governance features.
Data and Interoperability Exchange	HL7 FHIR Accelerator Vulcan	https://github.com/HL7/vulcan-rwd	Refer to section 4.1 FHIR to OMOP data transfer of the IDERHA Data Standard Manual
	CDISC SDTM data sets into OMOP-CDM transformer	https://www.cdisc.org/standards/foundational/adam	Refer to section 4.2 CDISC to OMOP transformer of the IDERHA Data Standard Manual
	Schema Validation	https://github.com/octavianN/Schematron-step-by-step	Refer to section 4.3 CDISC to OMOP transformer of the IDERHA Data Standard Manual
	DICOM to Image CDM	https://github.com/HIRC-SNUBH/ImagingCDM	Automated pipeline that transforms medical imaging data from the DICOM format to the OMOP-CDM format, followed by storing the converted data in a SQL database.
	Convert-Pheno	https://github.com/CNAG-Biomedical-Informatics/convert-pheno	Facilitates the conversion between various common data models for phenotypic data, including Beacon v2 Models, CDISC-ODM, OMOP-CDM, Phenopackets v2, and REDCap.
Data Analytics/Quality Assessment	Atlas tool	https://github.com/OHDSI/Atlas	Tool for researchers to conduct scientific analyses on OMOP-CDM data. Researchers can create cohorts by defining groups of people based on exposure to a drug or diagnosis of a particular condition using healthcare claims data. ATLAS has vocabulary searching of medical concepts to identify people with specific conditions, drug exposures etc.
	HADES	https://github.com/OHDSI/Hades	Utilizes advanced analytics to conduct characterization, estimate causal effects at the population level, and make predictions at the patient level on OMOP-CDM data. It is designed to function across various technical environments, including different operating systems and database platforms, and employs continuous integration with a comprehensive suite of unit tests to ensure reliability.
	Data Quality Dashboard (DQD)	https://ohdsi.github.io/DataQualityDashboard/	Tool for assessing and evaluating the quality of OMOP-CDM data. It executes a series of data quality checks on an OMOP-CDM instance, systematically assessing these checks against predefined thresholds and presenting the results clearly and transparently.
	Achilles	https://github.com/OHDSI/Achilles	Offers descriptive statistics for CDM databases. Facilitates the characterization, quality evaluation, and visualization of observational health databases. It also provides an interactive and

			exploratory framework that allows them to analyze patient demographics, assess the prevalence of conditions, medications, and procedures, and examine the distribution of clinical observation values.
	ARES	https://github.com/OHDSI/Ares	A Research Exploration System, It is designed to enhance the transparency of observational data research. It is an opinionated framework that outlines three levels of observational data evaluation and offers tools to tackle various research topics, including data characterization and data quality assessment.
	CohortMethod	https://ohdsi.github.io/CohortMethod/	Designed for conducting cohort studies within an observational database that adheres to the OMOP CDM. It extracts essential data from databases formatted in this model and utilizes a comprehensive array of covariates for both treatment and outcome models, including all medications, diagnoses, and procedures, as well as factors like age and comorbidity indices.
Vocabulary/Metadata Repository	ATHENA	https://github.com/OHDSI/Athena	Athena is a searchable database managed by the OHDSI that assists researchers in identifying codes and aligning them with their standard equivalents in the OMOP. Researchers can use Athena to search for specific domains and conditions.
	Ontology Lookup Service (OLS)	https://bio.tools/ols	A centralized repository for biomedical ontologies, designed to offer users straightforward access to the most current ontology versions. Users can explore these ontologies via the website or access them programmatically through the OLS API.

FAIR Data Management	FAIR Cookbook	https://faircookbook.elixir-europe.org/	A collection of recipes that provide guidance and processes to make and keep the data FAIR. It provides guidance and technical reviews to cover the required steps for FAIR data management.
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